

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

ALTERNATIVE MEASURES OF CENTRAL TENDENCY

Cvetkov V.

PhD., Tochnost Ltd.

1320, 50 Stephan Stambolov str.

Bankya, Bulgaria

ORCID: 0000-0001-9628-6768

Abstract

This paper presents two new estimators of the expectation of a random variable X , which are also unbiased and consistent as an arithmetic mean but more efficient. The first one is called center owing to the fact that its value is usually located between the mean and the median of the analyzed data. The second one is called C2 statistic. Both statistics are weighted averages. The center and C2 are computed with weights which are functions of the remoteness of each observation from other. Thus, these statistics use all available data in contrast to the median or a trimmed mean. They are less sensitive to the effect of outliers than the arithmetic mean because of the fact that the outlying observations receive smaller weights than these which are close to the median. The article presents mathematical and empirical proofs of the above statements.

Keywords: weighted average; expectation; efficiency

Introduction

Suppose a discrete random variable X takes values X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n and P is the probability mass function of X . Then, the expectation $E[X]$ is a number which can be given by (1).

$$E[X] = \sum_{i=1}^n X_i P(X = X_i) = X_1 P_1 + X_2 P_2 + \dots + X_n P_n \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) implies that the expected value $E[X]$ is a weighted average. Giving different values of P_i one can yield different values of $E[X]$. Suppose X_1 and X_n are the minimum and the maximum values in the set, respectively. If $P_1 = 1$ and $P_2 = P_3 = \dots = P_n = 0$, then $E[X] = X_1$ or the expected value will be equal to the smallest observation. If $P_n = 1$ and $P_1 = P_2 = \dots = P_{n-1} = 0$, then $E[X] = X_n$ or the expectation will be the largest observation. If n is an even number and $P_{n/2} = 0.5, P_{n/2+1} = 0.5$ and all other $P_i = 0$ then the expectation will be the median of the data set. $E[X]$ will also be equal to the median if n is an odd number, $P_{\text{int}(n/2)+1} = 1$ and all other $P_i = 0$. Suppose $P_1 = P_2 = \dots = P_n = 1/n$, then the expected value will be the arithmetic mean of all observations. Since $P_1 + P_2 + \dots + P_n = 1$ in each of the above mentioned cases one can conclude that all statistics, such as mean, median, largest observation, smallest observation are unbiased estimators of the expected value $E[X]$. Both the largest and the smallest observations in a data set do not give information about the centre of a distribution. Also these statistics do not take into account all observations in a data set. Owing to these facts they are not appropriate for describing of central tendency.

The median of a data set also neglects all observations except the middle one or two but present the central tendency better than the mean in these cases when there are outliers in data or the graph of a distribution is strongly skewed. In addition, the standard error of the median is 1.25 times greater than this of the arithmetic mean assuming a normality of distribution. As a result,

the median is estimated as a less accurate estimator than the mean [4, p.94].

It seems that the mean of a data set is the most appropriate statistic for describing of the centre of a distribution [1, 2, 4], among others. It should be remarked that the mean has a great drawback. This statistic derives from equal weighting of all observations. That is to say, the furthest observations and these which are close to the centre of a distribution are treated in the same manner. Let σ is the standard deviation of a data set and ε is a very small real number, such as ε tends to 0. Using equal weights supposes the correctness of (2). The last is obviously in contradiction with (1).

$$P(E[X] + 3\sigma - \varepsilon < X < E[X] + 3\sigma + \varepsilon) = P(E[X] - \varepsilon < X < E[X] + \varepsilon) \quad (2)$$

This approach might be reasonable when the analyzed data have a perfect uniform distribution but seems inappropriate in other cases, especially for skewed bell-shaped distributions or when the size of a data set is not great. In order to reduce the effect of extreme observations over estimated parameters, various technics are utilized by researches, e.g., transformations, truncation, robust procedures, etc. Most of these treatments are based on data cleaning [3].

As was supposed above the expected value $E[X]$ is a kind of a weighted average and can be given by a common equation (3).

$$\bar{X} = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot X_i / \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \quad (3)$$

According to [1, 5], the weighted average has a minimum variance $\text{Var}(\bar{X})$, which can be given by (4), when the weights w_i are inverse proportional to the variances of the observations (5).

$$\text{Var}(\bar{X}) = c / \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \quad (4)$$

$$w_i = c / \text{Var}(X_i) \quad (5)$$

The coefficient c in (4) and (5) is a coefficient of proportion by means of the weighted sample variance given by (6).

$$c = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot (X_i - \bar{X})^2 / (n - 1) \quad (6)$$

If one puts (6) into (4) then the final formula of the minimum variance of a weighted average can be written as (7) [4, p.94].

$$Var(\bar{X}) = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot (X - \bar{X})^2 / [(n - 1) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n w_i] \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) must easily be yielded by a parametric least squares adjustment [1, p.182]. If $w_1 = w_2 = \dots w_n = 1$ then equation (7) turns to (9).

Using the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality it is easy to prove (8) [5].

$$Var(\bar{X}) = c / \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \leq \sum_{i=1}^n w_i^2 \cdot Var(X_i) / (\sum_{i=1}^n w_i)^2 \quad (8)$$

Based on equations (3) and (7) one can see that any weighted average is an unbiased and consistent estimator of the expected value $E[X]$. Equation (8) shows that a weighted average is more efficient than an arithmetic mean when the variances of observations are known due to the fact that the weights used for calculation of the arithmetic mean are a function of the size of the data set but not of the variances of observations.

More complicated is the case when the variances of observations are unknown. In order to solve this problem one usually takes $w_1 = w_2 = \dots = w_n = 1$. Thus, the variance of the arithmetic mean can be given by (9).

$$Var(\text{arithmetic mean}) = n \cdot Var(X) / n^2 = Var(X) / n \quad (9)$$

If we replace the right side of (8) with (9) we will obtain (10).

$$Var(\bar{X}) = c / \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \leq Var(X) / n \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) clearly shows that there is a weighted average estimator of the expected value that has less variance than the well-known arithmetic mean. Thus, there is a more efficient estimator of $E[X]$. Such two new estimators of the expectancy are presented in the chapter below.

C2 Statistic

Suppose a discrete random variable X takes values X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n . We will show that each data point X_i can be presented as a function of other data points. Thus, the variance of each X_i is related with the variances of the rest variables $X_{j \neq i}$.

Proposition 1. If X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n ($n \geq 2$) are uncorrelated random variables with finite non-zero variances, then

$$X_i = \sum_{j=1}^n X_j \cdot D_{i,j} / \sum_{j=1}^n D_{i,j} \quad (11)$$

where:

$$D_{i,i} = \sum_{j=1}^n (X_i - X_j)^2 \quad (12)$$

$$D_{i,j} = \sum_{k=1}^n (X_i - X_k) \cdot (X_j - X_k) \quad (13)$$

Note: If observations X_k are random results from k measurements of a quantity X^{true} than the differences $X_i - X_j$ are differences between the true errors e_i and e_j of X_i and X_j , because of the relation $X_i - X_j = X^{\text{true}} + e_i - (X^{\text{true}} + e_j) = X^{\text{true}} + e_i - X^{\text{true}} - e_j = e_i - e_j$.

Proof of Proposition 1.

The proof below will concern X_1 variable. Due to the fact that the variables can be reordered, the equations below will be true for each variable X_i . Let $n=2$, then

$$X_1 = (X_1 \cdot D_{1,1} + X_2 \cdot D_{1,2}) / (D_{1,1} + D_{1,2}) \quad (14)$$

$$X_1 \cdot D_{1,1} + X_1 \cdot D_{1,2} = X_1 \cdot D_{1,1} + X_2 \cdot D_{1,2}$$

$$X_1 \cdot D_{1,2} - X_2 \cdot D_{1,2} = 0$$

$$(X_1 - X_2) \cdot D_{1,2} = (X_1 - X_2) \cdot [(X_1 - X_1) \cdot (X_2 - X_1) + (X_1 - X_2) \cdot (X_2 - X_2)] = 0$$

$$(X_1 - X_2) \cdot [0 \cdot (X_2 - X_1) + (X_1 - X_2) \cdot 0] = 0$$

$$0 = 0$$

Let $n=3$, then

$$X_1 = (X_1 \cdot D_{1,1} + X_2 \cdot D_{1,2} + X_3 \cdot D_{1,3}) / (D_{1,1} + D_{1,2} + D_{1,3}) \quad (15)$$

$$X_1 \cdot D_{1,1} + X_1 \cdot D_{1,2} + X_1 \cdot D_{1,3} = X_1 \cdot D_{1,1} + X_2 \cdot D_{1,2} + X_3 \cdot D_{1,3}$$

$$(X_1 - X_2) \cdot D_{1,2} + (X_1 - X_3) \cdot D_{1,3} = 0$$

$$(X_1 - X_2) \cdot [(X_1 - X_1) \cdot (X_2 - X_1) + (X_1 - X_2) \cdot (X_2 - X_2) + (X_1 - X_3) \cdot (X_2 - X_3)] +$$

$$+ (X_1 - X_3) \cdot [(X_1 - X_1) \cdot (X_3 - X_1) + (X_1 - X_2) \cdot (X_3 - X_2) + (X_1 - X_3) \cdot (X_3 - X_3)] = 0$$

$$(X_1 - X_2) \cdot [0 + 0 + (X_1 - X_3) \cdot (X_2 - X_3)] + (X_1 - X_3) \cdot [0 + (X_1 - X_2) \cdot (X_3 - X_2) + 0] = 0$$

$$(X_1 - X_2) \cdot (X_1 - X_3) \cdot (X_2 - X_3) + (X_1 - X_3) \cdot (X_1 - X_2) \cdot (X_3 - X_2) = 0$$

$$(X_1 - X_2) \cdot (X_1 - X_3) \cdot (X_2 - X_3) - (X_1 - X_2) \cdot (X_1 - X_3) \cdot (X_2 - X_3) = 0$$

$$0 = 0$$

Using the same logic, let $n = n$, then

$$X_1 = (X_1 \cdot D_{1,1} + \dots + X_n \cdot D_{1,n}) / (D_{1,1} + \dots + D_{1,n}) \quad (16)$$

$$X_1 \cdot D_{1,1} + X_1 \cdot D_{1,2} + X_1 \cdot D_{1,3} + \dots + X_1 \cdot D_{1,n} = X_1 \cdot D_{1,1} + X_2 \cdot D_{1,2} + X_3 \cdot D_{1,3} + \dots + X_n \cdot D_{1,n}$$

$$(X_1 - X_2) \cdot D_{1,2} + (X_1 - X_3) \cdot D_{1,3} + \dots + (X_1 - X_n) \cdot D_{1,n} = 0$$

$$(X_1 - X_2) \cdot [(X_1 - X_1) \cdot (X_2 - X_1) + (X_1 - X_2) \cdot (X_2 - X_2) + (X_1 - X_3) \cdot (X_2 - X_3) + \dots + (X_1 - X_n) \cdot (X_2 - X_n)] +$$

$$(X_1 - X_3) \cdot [(X_1 - X_1) \cdot (X_3 - X_1) + (X_1 - X_2) \cdot (X_3 - X_2) + (X_1 - X_3) \cdot (X_3 - X_3) + \dots + (X_1 - X_n) \cdot (X_3 - X_n)] +$$

.....

$$(X_1 - X_n) \cdot [(X_1 - X_1) \cdot (X_n - X_1) + (X_1 - X_2) \cdot (X_n - X_2) + (X_1 - X_3) \cdot (X_n - X_3) + \dots + (X_1 - X_n) \cdot (X_n - X_n)] = 0$$

After some algebraic manipulations of the above equation one will end up to $0 = 0$.

Therefore, equation (1) is true. Based on Proposition 1, we can define Proposition 2.

Proposition 2. If X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n ($n \geq 2$) are uncorrelated random variables with finite non-zero variances, then each variable X_i can be defined as a function of other variables X_j

$$X_i = \sum_{j \neq i} X_j \cdot D_{i,j} / \sum_{i \neq j} D_{i,j} \quad (17)$$

where:

$$D_{i,j} = \sum_{k=\{1,2,\dots,n\} \setminus \{i,j\}} (X_i - X_k) \cdot (X_j - X_k) \quad (18)$$

Proof of Proposition 2.

Again, the proof will be done for X_1 . Let start with equation (16).

$$X_1 = (X_1 \cdot D_{1,1} + X_2 \cdot D_{1,2} + \dots + X_n \cdot D_{1,n}) / (D_{1,1} + D_{1,2} + \dots + D_{1,n})$$

$$X_1 \cdot (D_{1,1} + D_{1,2} + \dots + D_{1,n}) = X_1 \cdot D_{1,1} + X_2 \cdot D_{1,2} + \dots + X_n \cdot D_{1,n}$$

$$X_1 \cdot D_{1,2} + X_1 \cdot D_{1,3} + \dots + X_1 \cdot D_{1,n} = X_2 \cdot D_{1,2} + X_3 \cdot D_{1,3} + \dots + X_n \cdot D_{1,n}$$

$$X_1 \cdot (D_{1,2} + D_{1,3} + \dots + D_{1,n}) = X_2 \cdot D_{1,2} + X_3 \cdot D_{1,3} + \dots + X_n \cdot D_{1,n}$$

Therefore, we can write (19).

$$X_1 = \sum_{j \neq 1} X_j \cdot D_{1,j} / \sum_{i \neq 1} D_{1,j} \quad (19)$$

If we can write (19) for X_1 , then we can write (17) for each variable in the analyzed set.

Consequently, the variance of each variable can be presented by the variances of the other variables and coefficients $D_{i,j}$. In case of X_1 we can write (20).

$$\text{Var}(X_1) = \left(\frac{D_{1,2}}{\sum_{j \neq 1} D_{1,j}} \right)^2 \cdot \text{Var}(X_2) + \dots + \left(\frac{D_{1,n}}{\sum_{j \neq 1} D_{1,j}} \right)^2 \cdot \text{Var}(X_n) \quad (20)$$

Suppose that $\text{Var}(X_2) = \text{Var}(X_3) = \dots = \text{Var}(X_n) = \sigma^2$, then (20) turns in (21).

$$\text{Var}(X_1) = \sigma^2 \cdot \sum_{j \neq 1} D_{1,j}^2 / \left(\sum_{j \neq 1} D_{1,j} \right)^2 \quad (21)$$

Based on this logic for the variance of the variable X_i one can write (22).

$$\text{Var}(X_i) = \sigma^2 \cdot \sum_{j \neq i} D_{i,j}^2 / \left(\sum_{j \neq i} D_{i,j} \right)^2 \quad (22)$$

Equation (22) clearly shows that if $X_i = X_j$ then $\text{Var}(X_i) = \text{Var}(X_j)$. Otherwise, $\text{Var}(X_i) \neq \text{Var}(X_j)$. In order to calculate an weighted average of the set $X_1, X_2,$

\dots, X_n by (7) one needs to obtain the weight of each variable. Using equation (22) these weights can be given by (23).

$$w_i = \left(\sum_{j \neq i} D_{i,j} \right)^2 / \sum_{j \neq i} D_{i,j}^2 \quad (23)$$

Using weights (23) in equation (3) one will obtain a new statistic, which is called C2. As can be seen C2 is based on the differences among true errors of data points. In this manner, each observation receives a weight with accordance to its deviation from other observations.

C1 or Center Statistic

One might have seen that there is a situation where equation (23) cannot be calculated, i.e. its denominator is equal to 0. This situation occurs when $n-1$ observations are equal each other but one observation differs from them. In this case the different observation should be removed or a new approach of calculating of weights should be used.

As has been proved above, the variance of each data point in a data set can be presented as a function of variances of other observations. Therefore, the data set defines the variance of each observation. The closer is a data point to the expectation the smaller is its variance. Physically this relation can be presented with the sum of the squares of distances from a given observation to other. This relation is described with equation (12). Based on this fact, one can obtain weights (24).

$$w_i = 1/D_{i,i} \quad (24)$$

So, if one uses weights (24) in equation (3) they will obtain a new statistic, which is named C1 or center statistic. This statistic is usually located between the arithmetic mean and the median of a given data set. It is important to be remarked that there is a functional correlation between weights (23) and (24). As a result, both C2 and center will give practically the same results when the size of data is great. All these statements will be proved with the examples below.

Example 1

Let we have the data set: **12, 14, 14, 15, 20**. Using equations (12) and (13) one can calculate the coefficients D_{ij} as given in Table 1.

Table 1

Coefficients D_{ij}				
D _{ij}				
81	51	51	36	-39
51	41	41	36	11
51	41	41	36	11
36	36	36	36	36
-39	11	11	36	161

In order to check Proposition 2 we will use the values in the first row of Table 1, which correspond to the first data point, i.e. 12. So, one can calculate that (14 x

51 + 14 x 51 + 15 x 36 + 20 x -39) / (51 + 51 + 36 + -39) = 1188 / 99 = 12.

In case of the second observation, i.e. 14, we have $(12 \times 51 + 14 \times 41 + 15 \times 36 + 20 \times 11) / (51 + 41 + 36 + 11) = 1946 / 139 = 14$. For the rest observations one is able to check Proposition 2 by themselves.

Using equations (23) and (24) we can compute the weights of each data point concerning both C2 and the center statistic. These weights are given in Table 2.

Table 2

Weights of the data set from Example 1 calculated by equations (23) and (24)

Weights	
(24)	(23)
0.01235	1.22222
0.02439	3.39024
0.02439	3.39024
0.02778	4.00000
0.00621	0.11801

If one calculates the coefficient of correlation R between the weights in the first and the second columns in Table 2 they will find that $R=1$. Thus, there is a functional correlation between weights (23) and (24). We

are going to restrict ourselves to prove this fact only in an empirical mode for now and focus on the values of the mean, C2, center and median of our data set. Their values and standard errors are given in Table 3.

Table 3

Mean, C2, Center and Median of the data

	Mean	C2	Center	Median
Value	15.00	14.19	14.42	14.00
SE	1.342	0.512	0.863	

According to Table 3, both statistics C2 and the center have less standard errors than the arithmetic mean. Thus, they are more efficient estimators of an expectation $E[X]$ in case of the data set of Example 1. It can be seen that they are located between the mean and the median but tend to the median.

520 660 730 810 820 865 890 915 975 1000
 1050 1080 1160 1210 1740
 1800 1820 2200 2200 2300 2450 2500 2550
 2600 2650 2700 3400 4450

Example 2

Suppose the data set below contains the monthly wages of 28 randomly selected employees in a company.

The mean, C2, the center and the median wage values with their standard errors are given in Table 4.

Table 4

Mean, C2, Center and Median of Example 2 data

	Mean	C2	Center	Median
Value	1715.9	1625.9	1631.1	1475.0
SE	182.8	141.4	144.2	

As can be seen from Table 4, C2 and the center have close values and standard errors. Both statistics are located between the median and the arithmetic

mean of the analyzed data set and their standard errors are less than the standard error of the mean.

Table 5

Weights (23) and (24) of each observation concerning Example 2

Number	(23)	(24)	Number	(23)	(24)
1	0.60788	0.63071	15	1.66783	1.62896
2	0.71252	0.72926	16	1.65549	1.61733
3	0.77156	0.78486	17	1.64841	1.61067
4	0.84475	0.85379	18	1.31220	1.29403
5	0.85433	0.86281	19	1.31220	1.29403
6	0.89860	0.90450	20	1.19420	1.18290
7	0.92400	0.92843	21	1.02192	1.02064
8	0.94997	0.95288	22	0.96771	0.96959
9	1.01445	1.01361	23	0.91559	0.92051
10	1.04214	1.03969	24	0.86574	0.87355
11	1.09881	1.09306	25	0.81824	0.82882
12	1.13349	1.12572	26	0.77313	0.78633
13	1.22754	1.21430	27	0.35603	0.39352
14	1.28662	1.26994	28	0.12466	0.17562

Table 5 contains a modification (25) of weights (23) and (24) of each observation of the example data, where n is the size of the data set. Modification (25) does not change the final results but modifies the weights in such manner that they will be around 1. Thus, the sum of all weights will be equal to n .

$$w'_i = n \cdot w_i / \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \quad (25)$$

If one calculates the coefficient of correlation R between the weights in both columns of Table 5 they will find that $R=1$. Thus, the functional correlation between weights (23) and (24) is also supported by these data. Table 5 also illustrates the ratios among the weights of the central data points and those close to the periphery of the distribution of our data. One can see that the highest wage of 4450 currency unit, which is in

the range from 2σ to 3σ and cannot be treated as an outlier, has the least weight in case of C2 and the center. As a result, its effect over these statistics is less than the arithmetic mean. This data point also inflates the standard error of the mean. If this observation is trimmed the mean will be equal to 1614.6 with a standard error of 158.0 currency units, values which are close to the C2 and the center and their standard errors.

Example 3

In order to illustrate that with increasing of the size of a data set the difference between C2 and the center tends to zero, the values of discussed statistics and their standard errors are given in Table 6 below. The values in Table 6 are based on six random number generations from uniform distribution with the lowest and the highest values 0 and 100, respectively.

Table 6

Means, C2-s, Centers and Medians, derived from random simulations of U(0, 100)					
Number of observations	Description	Mean	C2	Center	Median
10	Value	56.00	62.05	60.97	71.86
	SE	11.93	10.01	10.41	
25	Value	49.51	49.74	49.75	50.10
	SE	5.78	4.47	4.57	
50	Value	50.39	52.61	52.54	53.28
	SE	4.04	3.16	3.19	
100	Value	50.52	51.50	51.49	52.92
	SE	2.99	2.43	2.44	
150	Value	48.38	48.15	48.15	48.05
	SE	2.37	1.90	1.90	
200	Value	47.07	46.68	46.68	44.98
	SE	2.17	1.78	1.78	

If one performs some similar experiment(s) they will yield different values from those given in Table 6. The same will be two facts:

- If the size of a data set is getting bigger the values and standard errors of C2 and the center will be getting closer.
- The standard errors of C2 and the center will always be less than the standard error of the mean concerning any data set.

Conclusion

The current article shows that an arithmetic mean is not the most efficient estimator of an expectancy. The mean is a time-proven estimator but really sensitive to effect of outliers and fringeliers due to the equal weighting of all observations in a data set. The classical weighting relies on the fact that the sample derives from population which kernel is bell-shaped and almost symmetric around the expectation and as a result, the tail observations in both sides mutually eliminate their common effect over the expectation. Also a huge number of observations is supposed. The above assumptions are not always met in the practice. So, the equal weighting is a good approximation of the best weights

but more artificial and subjective. As shown by Proposition 2 above, the variance of each observation is a function of the variances of other observations in a data set. Consequently, data points determine by themselves which of them are outliers, accepted members or mid-values. Let we follow our data.

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